

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

 @pinagpalapublishingservices **Search**

 pinagpala_publishing **Search**

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com **Search**

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), p.63, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Teachers' ICT Competence and Pupils' Academic Outcomes: Evidence from *Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan*

JOCELYN M. BACANTO, LPT, MAIE

Teacher III/Teacher-in-Charge

San Felipe Elementary School

Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

Abstract

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in basic education is increasingly recognized as essential for improving teaching and learning outcomes. This study examined the effectiveness of ICT in teaching *Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan* (EPP) among Grade IV to VI pupils in selected elementary schools of the North District, City Division of Ilagan during School Year 2017–2018. Employing a descriptive–correlational design, the study assessed teachers' user-ability of ICT resources, ways of computer use, attitudes toward ICT, training, and institutional support, and correlated these factors with pupils' academic performance. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and documentary analysis, and analyzed using weighted means and correlation statistics. Findings indicate that teachers generally possess positive attitudes and satisfactory ICT skills, but face limitations in training and access to resources. Despite these challenges, ICT use was found to support improved pupil performance, particularly in enhancing engagement and skill development. The results suggest that ICT integration is a valuable tool for strengthening classroom instruction but requires sustained professional development and equitable access to resources. This study provides insights for curriculum developers, school administrators, and policymakers in enhancing ICT-driven education.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, *Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan*, teacher competence, ICT integration, academic performance outcomes, student perceptions of learning, Philippine education system

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17271657

